

THE EFFECT OF FLIPPED CLASSROOM MODEL USING TELEGRAM BOT IN TEACHING BASIC CHEMISTRY

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ABSTRACT

It is required for all educational components to use online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. The flipped classroom model with social media can be an excellent way to implement the changes necessary for the modern educational environment, particularly Telegram. This study analyzed how a flipped classroom using a telegram bot for basic chemistry instruction fared during the COVID-19 outbreak. The research participants were 40 students from SMAN 1 Gondangwetan Pasuruan. They were split into experimental and control classes; each group consisted of twenty students. Using the questionnaire, the data from the pre-test and post-test were also gathered and analyzed. Data were examined using two average difference tests and descriptive quantitative percentages (Mann-Whitney test). The findings demonstrated that experimental classes improved students' cognitive learning outcomes. About 95% of the N-Gain scores were examined in the test group, compared to 70% in the control class. According to the Mann-Whitney test, the control and experiment classes are significantly different, which supported the finding with a significant value of $0.041 < 0.05$. It has been demonstrated that the model enhances students' academic performance.

KEYWORDS

Flipped Classroom, Telegram Bot, Chemistry, Teaching, Active Learning

INTRODUCTION

Online learning is mandatory and implemented by all students and educators at various levels of education during the pandemic of COVID-19. Online learning has rapidly grown since 2020 due to the pandemic of COVID-19 that has affected the changes in global conditions. Such conditions require teachers to create an effective and efficient learning process by applying appropriate methods or approaches. The most popular new pedagogical approach is flipped classroom practice in online learning activities.

The flipped classroom model is a powerful idea to carry out the reforms required by the education age. This model focuses on group learning rather than individual learning. The learning model was the opposite of the usual learning method applied by the teachers in the classroom. In lesson class, teachers provide materials and give homework as a follow-up. However, this flipped classroom model presents a different way of teaching. Teachers can provide the learning materials outside of the lesson class. Hence, the students needed to study the learning documents given before class (asynchronous learning). In the flipped classroom learning model, the applied strategy can increase interactions between the student and the teachers or fellow students. Additionally, the use of technology in providing supplementary materials reduces the teacher's direct instruction (Damayanti & Sutarna, 2016).

Nowadays, almost every person has access to social media. One of the popular social media platforms is Telegram. Telegram features provide security and ease of use. Combining the flipped classroom model with social media as a learning medium will facilitate the learning process. The Telegram bot as a learning medium for basic chemistry may perhaps help the preparation of active learning and class coordination. Muniroh and Rizdania (2021) report the learning media developed for basic chemistry and note that the users can perform the telegram bot smoothly. Both the teachers and students responded to the telegram bot to satisfy them in facilitating the learning activity. On the contrary, applying the Telegram bot as a learning medium can be an efficient alternative during an online class.

Moreover, classroom learning sessions, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, are conducted through the virtual classroom with synchronous discussions and work on tasks during lesson hours. McCarthy (2016) reports that students can learn independently using flipped classrooms that encourage them to adjust to their new learning experience. Also, Rindaningsih (2018) shows that the flipped classroom model strongly influences honing student skills and makes students highly aware and responsible for participating in learning activities. Another report by Handayani et al. (2021) found that the flipped classroom model accommodates the teachers to present the materials and lead the students to solve problems during the lesson. Also, students can correlate the concepts with their knowledge and discuss the existing cases in the group. This study aims to describe the effect of a flipped classroom model using a telegram bot in teaching basic chemistry, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

The current study examined the effect of the flipped classroom model by giving a pre-test at the beginning of class and a post-test after the lesson. The pre-test and post-test were measured and compared between the control and experimental classes. The experiment class applied the flipped classroom model (synchronous and asynchronous), whereas the control class carried out traditional learning (synchronous).

Study Groups

This research subject involved students at SMAN 1 Gondangwetan Pasuruan in the 2021/2022 school year. This research population is all students in the XI grade of Mathematics and Natural Science (MIPA). About 40 students participated in experimental and control classes, each class consisting of 20 students. The purpose of the sampling technique is to recruit the subject. The data consisted of pre-test and post-test results and the student efficacy scale. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive quantitative percentages and two average difference tests.

Data Analysis

The study aimed to describe the effect of a flipped classroom model using bot telegram in teaching basic chemistry. The data collected were analyzed using an independent sample t-test. An independent samples t-test is a statistical tool used to compare the mean score of two different groups. However, one of the prerequisites for using parametric tests is the assumption that the data is distributed normally and that of a large sample (at least 30 people in groups) (Burak, 2017).

Given the number of individuals in the groups under 30, descriptive quantitative percentages and two average difference tests (Mann-Whitney test) are used to examine the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cognitive Learning Outcomes

The pre-test and post-test questionnaires are used to evaluate cognitive learning. Based on Table 1, the pre-test score of the experiment class is lower than the control class, with averages of 39 and 46.25. Contrarily, the experiment class had higher post-test scores with 79.75 than the control class with 71. The condition of the experiment class indicated an increase in cognitive functioning when practicing the flipped classroom model with telegram media. Furthermore, the control class that applied to conventional learning had a lower post-test score.

Table 1. Students' Pre-test and Post-test Scores

	Experimental class		Control Class	
	Pretest	Posttest	Pretest	Posttest
Highest score	50	95	65	85
Lowest score	20	60	30	55
Average score	39	79,75	46,25	71

The learners have little information about basic chemistry, so this causes experiment and control classes to gain a low pre-test score. According to Khuen (2019), students should not be expected to know all the answers on a pre-test; instead, they should be expected to use prior knowledge to predict logical solutions. As associated with Fortuno and Richafort (2020), low performance on the pre-test may be anticipated, given that the learners still lack fundamental knowledge of the materials. As a result, a learning strategy that can help students fully comprehend the subject is required to enhance learning results.

Students who participate in classes using the flipped classroom model get the chance to conduct independent learning before class. However, using Telegram bots as a medium, students can have group discussions about the subject matter or engage with the instructors directly when they run into a challenging situation. Additionally, the Telegram bot has documents and videos on the subject related. These attributes aid the student in carrying out additional studies. According to prior research by Muniroh and Rizdania (2021), who created the Telegram bot for learning fundamental chemistry, the program is beneficial and fulfills user expectations. Thus, employing Telegram as a learning tool for basic chemistry and implementing the learning model ensured that student learning results would increase.

Additionally, because traditional education does not allow students to learn about fundamental chemistry on their own, students are less motivated to study. The motivation for learning among the students in the control class is based on traditional learning techniques. The teacher-centered learning strategies bore the students without any component of student participation. As seen by the fact that the experimental class outperformed the control class on the post-test despite the preceding students' pre-test scores being higher.

The learning process creates habits in students that influence the improvement of cognitive learning outcomes. For example, the post-test results in the experimental class prove that self-study materials are claimed to boost students' ability to learn independently. Another study by Handayani et al. (2021) found that using the flipped classroom paradigm allowed students to participate in class discussions while studying and may help them to understand more about the subject that affected their learning outcomes. According to Johnson (2013), the flipped classroom is a learning approach that prioritizes one-on-one contact while minimizing direct instruction. This tactic uses technology to give students access to more resources for learning both online and offline at any time and from any location. Students interact with project partners, practice skills, and get feedback on their development throughout instructional time in class. The N-gain score should also be calculated to assess the effect of improving students' cognitive learning outcomes.

Improved learning outcomes (N-Gain)

Comparing pre-test and post-test results reveals how students' learning outcomes have improved (N-Gain). Three N-Gain score categories are shown in Table 2 for the experimental and control classes. According to the data, most students in the experimental class can adapt the flipped classroom model to study basic chemistry. It is established that the learning model influences students' learning outcomes. The post-test results improved, as evidenced by the 95% of students who obtained moderate and high categories of N-Gain Score. Contrarily, only 60% of students in the control group could enhance their academic performance even though students' pre-test scores were more significant than those in the experimental class.

Table 2. Improvement of learning outcomes (N-Gain)

Class	N-gain	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Experimental	<0,3	Low	1	5
	0,3<N-gain<0,7	Moderate	10	50
	>0,7	High	9	45
Control	<0,3	Low	6	30
	0,3<N-gain<0,7	Moderate	12	60
	>0,7	High	2	10

In the experimental class, the telegram bots facilitate students' understanding of the information that the teacher has explained. Users' and stakeholders' requirements were estimated throughout the development of the Telegram bot. Materials, pre-tests, quizzes, answer keys, exciting facts, and videos relating to each basic chemistry topic are included in the various sections of the topic (Muniroh and Rizdania, 2021). Through this platform, students can communicate with their instructors and classmates at the same time. Besides, the platform makes it easier for students to access the fundamental chemical content at different times and locations. Thus Putri et al. (2022) assert that Google Classroom and the flipped classroom model can help students learn the biology material and watch related videos before class. Students may then begin discussing, exchanging information, and solving problems, which has a different impact on the experimental class than on the control class in terms of motivation to learn.

Table 3. Descriptives

	Classes		Statistic	Std. Error		
Posttest Score	Control Class	Mean	79,75	2,250		
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	75,04		
			Upper Bound	84,46		
		5% Trimmed Mean		80,00		
		Median		80,00		
		Variance		101,250		
		Std. Deviation		10,062		
		Minimum		60		
		Maximum		95		
		Range		35		
		Interquartile Range		14		
		Skewness		-,398	,512	
		Kurtosis		-,242	,992	
		Experiment Class	Experiment Class	Mean	71,00	2,071
				95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	66,67
	Upper Bound			75,33		
5% Trimmed Mean				71,11		
Median				72,50		
Variance				85,789		
Std. Deviation				9,262		
Minimum				55		
Maximum				85		
Range				30		
Interquartile Range				18		
Skewness				-,325	,512	
Kurtosis				-,849	,992	
Pretest	Control Class			Mean	46,25	2,203
				95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	41,64
			Upper Bound	50,86		
		5% Trimmed Mean		46,11		
		Median		45,00		
		Variance		97,039		
		Std. Deviation		9,851		
		Minimum		30		
		Maximum		65		
		Range		35		

Numerous variables contributed to the improvement of students learning outcomes, one being the students' interest in the learning material. According to the IRIS Research Centers in the US and Europe (2014), students who took part in traditional classes showed considerably improved learning outcomes in applying the conceptual measures of knowledge. In line with Habes et al. (2018) and Habes et al. (2019), using social media for communication in the classroom encourages students to investigate subject matter and engage with the material. It reveals that using a Telegram bot as a learning model had a much more substantial positive impact on student learning outcomes in the experimental class than in the control class. Those circumstances were most likely brought on by the student's eagerness and curiosity to participate in the learning paradigm. Additionally, it encourages autonomous study among the students. As per Sharif (2012), enthusiasm can inspire an individual or student to take action to reach their objective and feel content with their success.

Normality and homogeneity Test Results

It was determined that the pre-post test score had a significant level of $> 0,052$ based on the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The experimental class exhibited a normal distribution, according to the normality test. It indicated that the population had a pretest-posttest value that was normally distributed. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov analysis, with a significant level of $0,052$, was used in the normality test to evaluate the population's distribution level. The distribution is expected if the significance level is greater than 0.05 . However, if the normality test's significance level is less than 0.05 , the distribution is not normal (Nadun, 2017). The homogeneity test result indicated a significance level of $0.028 < 0.5$. As a result, the outcome showed that the data was not homogeneous. The Mann-Whitney test can be used to determine whether there is a variance in the significance of the data.

Table 4. Normality Test Results

Classes	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk			
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.	
Posttest Score	Control Class	,118	20	,200 [*]	,948	20	,335
	Experiment Class	,167	20	,145	,932	20	,172
Pretest	Control Class	,150	20	,200 [*]	,945	20	,299
	Experiment Class	,192	20	,052	,890	20	,027

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

According to the results of the Man-Whitney test, the pre-test and post-test results for the control and experimental classes are significantly different, with an Asymp value of 0.041 . This result is consistent with the N-gain score and the earlier pre-test and post-test results. The learning processes that involve the instructional materials at the level of remembering and understanding are appropriate for flipped classroom-based learning. The resources are individually investigated and used in the classroom to apply the philosophy of activity-based education (Lai & Hwang, 2016). The material needs to provide possibilities for fostering learner autonomy, and digital

technology is employed in both the information delivery and evaluation. Therefore, the material is a factor in the flipped classroom setting. The information in the e-learning design class is arranged according to complexity, going from the broadest to the most detailed.

Table 5. Homogeneity Test Results

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Posttest Score	Based on Mean	,028	1	38	,867
	Based on Median	,019	1	38	,892
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	,019	1	37,306	,892
	Based on trimmed mean	,019	1	38	,890
Pretest	Based on Mean	,028	1	38	,869
	Based on Median	,016	1	38	,899
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	,016	1	37,298	,899
	Based on trimmed mean	,011	1	38	,916

Table 6. Ranks

		Classes	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Posttest Score	Control Class		20	25,30	506,00
	Experiment Class		20	15,70	314,00
	Total		40		
Pretest	Control Class		20	24,20	484,00
	Experiment Class		20	16,80	336,00
	Total		40		

Table 7. Test Statistics

	Posttest Score	Pretest
Mann-Whitney U	104,000	126,000
Wilcoxon W	314,000	336,000
Z	-2,629	-2,039
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,009	,041
Exact Sig. [2*(1-tailed Sig.)]	,009 ^b	,046 ^b

a. Grouping Variable: Classes

b. Not corrected for ties.

Moreover, synchronous and asynchronous actions in the classroom must be taken into account. In the synchronous learning quadrant, students individually study utilizing text, audio documents, visual documents, audio-visual documents, animation, and simulations. Asynchronous class discussions were also enabled by the lecturer utilizing a WhatsApp group. In comparison, Zoom was used for the synchronous class in the second quadrant. According to Chaeruman (2020), all classroom activities fall under the link between learning experiences and learning quadrants.

The flipped classroom is one type of online learning that has developed in the last decade. Research related to flipped classrooms continues to evolve as learning opportunities that do not only rely on face-to-face. Some studies tended to show positive results, such as learning outcomes, learning independence, motivation, and satisfaction with the experience of using a flipped classroom. In short, a flipped classroom is a learning strategy that changes learning patterns by providing video lectures related to basic knowledge of learning materials to be studied at home. On the other hand, at school, students can focus on deepening the material (Bergmann & Sams, 2012). According to Herreid and Schiller (2013), class activities such as explaining the materials, giving assignments, exercises, and assignments, changed into flipped online-based learning. Also, the research by Nouri (2016) showed that most students felt optimistic about the flipped classroom. There was a strong correlation between that perspective and perceptions of higher motivation, engagement, enhanced learning, and effective learning.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the telegram bot is an alternative flipped classroom learning media that can help students to learn basic chemistry lessons. Due to pandemics, this model can be an effective learning solution that successfully transfers knowledge. It creates flexible learning environments by providing active learning activities and allowing students to assume individual learning responsibilities. Thus, that flipped classroom model can improve learning outcomes by pretest-posttest measurement. It indicated that bot telegram is effective in creating an efficient learning process. The model enables learners to acquire new skills and to cause radical changes in their learning habits.

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